

WORK STRAINS AND COPING RESPONSES FOR MOTIVATION AND COMMITMENT OF TEACHERS: BASIS FOR A PROPOSED STRESS MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Teaching is considered the noblest profession but requires numerous works demands. Due to this matter, it may lead to several work strains that may affect their performance at school. Hence, this study sought to determine and analyze the relationship of work strains and coping responses to motivation and commitment of teachers. To answer the hypothesis provided, the descriptive and correlational research design was utilized in the conduct of the study. Survey questionnaires in Google form served as the main instrument to gather the needed data. It was participated by one hundred twenty teacher-respondents from seven schools of Candelaria East District, Division of Quezon for the academic year of 2020-2021. After the analysis, the data gathered revealed that there is a significant relationship between work strains and coping responses to motivation and commitment of teachers. This signifies that decreasing the level of work strains and increasing effective coping response will intensify the motivation and commitment of the teacher-respondents towards work. Based on the findings and conclusions made in the study, the researcher recommends that the school administrators must proactively search for the means to minimize and alleviate work strains, strengthen coping response, and effectively provide information about stress management to upsurge and improve their motivation and commitment, which may result to increase and better-quality performance of teachers.

Keywords: Work Strains, Coping Responses, Motivation, Commitment